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Report of the first MCAA Canada Chapter meeting

District 3 Innovation Centre, Montréal, 28/02/2026

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Project LandVoICE (ID: 101202117)

LandVoice

Landscape vocabulary in the languages of Iran

1. Key takeaways

The event featured an introductory session led by Sergio Crespo-Garcia (Chair) and Catarina C. Ferreira (Vice-Chair), outlining the mission and vision of the Canada Chapter, as well as the rationale behind its foundation as a spin-off from the North America Chapter, aiming to reflect in a more granular way the shifting paradigms which are currently shaping science policies in different North American countries.

The welcome remarks by Adriana Gonzalez introduced us to the chosen venue – a beautiful co-working space located at the District 3 Innovation Centre in Montréal – and highlighted its nature as a hub providing concrete support to start-ups, entrepreneurial ventures, and individual researchers based in Québec.

The flash presentation session titled “A Glimpse at Your Career” allowed participant members to introduce themselves, showcasing the broad range of professional profiles and fields of expertise represented in this truly diverse (interdisciplinary, international, and intergenerational) MCAA Chapter.

The networking session was useful for establishing initial contacts with members involved in research projects within the same ERC sector or developed in

partnership with institutions in the same EU country/ies (Italy and France, in the case of LandVolCE). The initiative fully responded to the core interest expressed by the majority of Chapter members (85.7%, according to the MCAA Canada Chapter – Membership Survey 2025) in in-person networking opportunities.

With members almost evenly split between current fellows (42.9%) and alumni (57.1%), and even cases of double status, the meeting effectively supported the exchange of individual experiences, favouring an open discussion on shared issues regarding MSCA fellowships in the local and global context. It also encouraged current fellows to begin projecting themselves beyond the completion of their projects, and seriously reflect on future career prospects and intersectoral opportunities for researchers.

I found the openness of many alumni in sharing the difficulties encountered in their career paths – including the complications of multiple career shifts and relocations, or the frustration in developing one’s plurilingual competence or meeting the productivity requirements of academia – very stimulating for reflecting on my own experience and current place as a researcher.

The plenary sessions “EU–Canada Policy Dialogues and Transatlantic Collaboration” held by Agnieszka Weinar, and “Introducing MITACS Programs” held by Visou Adi, met the interest of most members (85.7%) in science policy news and updates, as well as in funding opportunities with a potential to facilitate research collaboration and mobility between Canada and the EU, or allowing for a return of international EU researchers to Canada after the completion of their MSCA fellowships.

The concerns for career and policy navigation expressed by the members were addressed during the meeting sessions, and the outcome of the debate was overall encouraging. However, the discussion with the Canadian Association of Postdoctoral Scholars led by Camille Rosseau and Chanelle Polenz highlighted that the professional role and innovation potential of postdoctoral researchers – particularly of MSCA Postdoctoral fellows – is still insufficiently recognized in Canada. Social security and benefits for Canada-based postdoctoral researchers, even with advanced levels of experience, may vary considerably depending on their position (as employees, trainees, or fellows) and based on factors such as funding type, scientific sector, host institution, or Province.

This emphasized, above all, the need to continue disseminating knowledge about Horizon Europe programs in Canada, but also the importance of advocating for a full recognition of postdoctoral research work, and of the MSCA postdoctoral

fellowship in particular, as a professional career stage rather than an extension of studentship, as per the European Charter for Researchers.

«I am grateful for the opportunity and the financial support offered by the MCAA to attend the inaugural meeting of its Canada Chapter in Montréal – also, my first MCAA meeting. It was an important occasion to discuss the future of the EU–Canada partnership in research, as well as a valuable chance for a thoughtful reflection on my own career trajectory. The event provided an excellent networking platform, bringing together incredibly committed people in a beautiful venue, and gave real life to the motto “bridging minds, building futures”»

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2. Funded expenses:

- Item 1: 151.92 euros (accommodation for one night, corresponding to 245.90 CAD including taxes)
- Item 2: 13.46 euros (lunch for the 27/02/2026, excluding alcoholic beverages. Corresponding to 21.79 CAD including taxes)

- Item 3: 156.74 euro (train tickets Ottawa-Montréal A/R, corresponding to 253.70 CAD including taxes)

= TOT 322.12 euros

3. Documentation of activities:

3.1 Venue

3.2 Meeting

